

STUDIES ON RANCIDITY OF BUTTERFAT. PART IX. THE ACTION OF METALS

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Of the metals tested, copper and iron are the strongest pro-oxidants. Tin and aluminium are relatively ineffective. The metallic soaps are stronger pro-oxidants than the corresponding metals, and when the metal is supplied in an aqueous phase in contact with fat, the rate is much slower. In absence of oxygen, the catalytic effect of the metals on the oxidation of the fat is not observed.

The pro-oxidant effect of certain metals, notably copper and iron, upon oils and fats has been known for many years, but the available information has been scattered and sometimes incomplete to be of much help to the fat industry. The relative activities of various common metals and alloys in accelerating rancidity is a matter of considerable practical importance, since the choice of material for construction of the processing plant, storage vessels and containers will largely depend on it. A brief resumé of the present state of knowledge concerning the behaviour of metals is given below.

Golding and Feilman (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1905, 24, 1285) observed that a "tallowy" odour developed in milk that was passed over a tinned copper cooler from which part of the plating had been worn away in use; moreover, contact with copper or brass or in less degree with iron was found to produce "tallowy" odour in butter (Hunziker and Hosman, *J. Dairy Sci.*, 1918, 1, 320). Very recently Paul, Bhalerao and Ananta-krishnan (*Ind. J. Dairy Sci.*, 1949, 2, 7) have carried out experiments on the storage of ghee in different types of containers. An attempt at correlation of the nature of particular metal with its solubility in weak organic acids in producing off-flavours in milk-products has been made by using different metallic equipments in creameries (Hunziker, Cordes and Niseen, *J. Dairy Sci.*, 1929, 12, 179). It was evaluated, from the measurement of the length of time necessary to produce rancidity in the cases of corn and cotten-seed oils and lard, when strips of metals were immersed in them, that copper was the most and tin and aluminium were the least active of the metals studied (Emery and Henley, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1922, 14, 937). Metallic oleates accelerated the bleaching of vegetable oils at 80° in descending order of efficiency in the series: Co, Mn, Cu, Ni, Pb and Fe (Rai, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1917, 36, 948). The addition of a soluble copper salt (Cu-stearate) at a concentration of 1 to 2 parts per million was shown to greatly increase the rate of peroxide formation in lard at 100° (King, Roschen and Irwin, *Oil & Soap*, 1933, 10, 105). A few similar experiments have also been done with milk and butter. Excepting these instances practically the whole of the published work has been concentrated on the effect of the addition of metals and salts to dry oils and fats, whereas most foodstuffs contain in addition to the fat an aqueous phase containing non-fatty materials. Lea (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1936, 55, 2937) studied the effect of certain metallic salts dissolved in aqueous phase in contact with lard and

observed that extremely minute amounts often had a marked influence on the rate of onset of rancidity which increased with the concentration of the metal.

The present study on the action of metals on fats has been divided into three sections :

- (i) Action of metals in metallic form studied by storage experiments in different metallic containers.
- (ii) Action of metals in solution, storage experiments carried out in pyrex glass vessels with addition of different metallic oleates.
- (iii) Addition of metals in aqueous solution, the effect of addition of water-soluble metallic salts (as sulphates) dissolved in aqueous phase in contact with butterfat.

The experimental results are summarised in Tables I, II and III.

TABLE I

Effect of storage of butterfat in different metallic containers.

Expt No.	Metal.	Peroxide and Kreis values after							
		15 days.		30 days.		45 days.		60 days.	
		P. V.	K.	P. V.	K.	P. V.	K.	P. V.	K.
1.	Aluminium	0.20	1.3	1.0	2.5	6.3	3.4	11.0	9.7
2.	Copper	0.50	2.0	9.3	17.4	28.7	27.0	33.1	20.0
3.	Iron	0.20	1.4	1.2	2.3	7.2	5.1	23.3	12.0
4.	Lead	0.27	1.4	1.1	2.5	7.2	4.5	20.0	10.5
5.	Nickel	0.5	1.4	1.8	2.8	7.3	6.1	21.4	15.0
6.	Tin	0.17	1.1	1.3	2.4	3.7	3.2	7.0	7.4
7.	Zinc	0.27	1.2	1.0	1.6	8.3	3.9	10.3	8.4
8.	Control	0.14	0.1	1.1	1.6	2.4	4.2	3.2	8.8

TABLE II

Effect of storage of butterfat in presence of metals in solution (as oleates).

Expt No.	Substance.	Conc. (p.p.m.)	Peroxide and Kreis values after							
			15 days.		30 days.		45 days.		60 days.	
			P.V.	K.	P.V.	K.	P.V.	K.	P.V.	K.
1.	Cobalt oleate	1	0.54	2.0	2.2	4.0	4.8	5.4	18.6	12.0
2.	Copper oleate	5	1.50	3.8	5.6	6.6	18.4	10.0	30.0	20.6
3.	Lead oleate	5	0.72	2.6	2.6	5.2	10.6	9.0	22.2	14.0
4.	Manganese oleate	5	0.72	2.1	2.2	4.2	4.6	6.4	12.8	10.2
5.	Iron oleate	5	1.0	2.6	3.2	5.6	8.4	9.8	19.5	21.0
6.	Nickel oleate	5	0.54	1.0	2.0	4.1	7.4	5.5	19.0	10.0
7.	Control	—	0.14	0.1	1.3	1.6	2.4	4.2	3.0	8.8

TABLE III

Effect of metals in aqueous phase in contact with butterfat on rancidity.

Expt No.	Metal.	Conc. (p.p.m)	15 days.		30 days		45 days.		60 days.	
			P.V.	K.	P.V.	K.	P.V.	K.	P.V.	K.
1.	Aluminium	25	0.22	1.1	0.95	2.2	2.0	2.2	3.0	2.4
2.	Chromium	"	0.21	1.7	0.98	2.3	2.3	3.2	5.4	5.4
3.	Copper	"	0.40	1.5	3.70	4.8	14.6	19.5	23.1	13.0
4.	Iron	"	1.23	3.2	8.7	7.2	16.6	12.4	30.3	18.4
5.	Nickel	"	0.27	1.0	0.5	1.2	1.9	2.2	2.2	2.2
6.	Zinc	"	0.10	0.3	0.96	1.2	1.9	2.0	3.0	2.7
7.	Control	"	0.27	0.3	1.89	—	2.4	—	3.55	—

It would appear from these tables that copper and iron are in general the strongest pro-oxidants of rancidity of butterfat, whether in metallic state or dissolved in the form of fatty acid soaps or present in solution in water phase in contact with the fat. Desirable results were obtained with tin, aluminium and zinc, and hence for all practical purposes tinned vessel may safely be used as materials for construction of the containers. Of the oleates studied, nickel is the least effective, although in general they are all pro-oxidants (Fig. 1). The samples stored in copper containers acquire a bluish green colour. In most of the samples, the yellow colour is completely bleached on storage.

FIG. 1

Curves 1-6 refer respectively to oleate of Cu, Co, Pb, Mn, Fe and Ni, and curve 7 refers to Control.

A close examination of the tables reveals that increase in autoxidation rate of fats by the metals possibly takes place by first dissolution of the metals in the fats by the free acids with formation of the soluble salts and these fatty acids soaps of the metals are the active catalysts in the process. When the metal is in the aqueous phase, the slower rate observed is possibly due to the slow rate of diffusion of the metallic ion

from the aqueous to the fat phase. The rate is maximum when the metal is provided in the form of the soluble salt, viz. the oleate. With the experiments on storage in the metallic containers the formation of peroxides at the end of 15 days is much smaller than in the experiments with the oleates, because in the first case a certain time must elapse before the free fatty acids are formed to attack the metallic containers and form the highly active soaps.

The effectiveness of a particular metal in accelerating the production of rancidity in the fats of foods brought in contact with it thus depends on the combined effect of surface activity, solubility and accelerating effect of the dissolved metal. This can be seen from the more accelerated behaviour of the metallic oleates in comparison with the metals themselves.

Next, it was considered important to study the effect of metals in absence of oxygen, with a view to observing its effectiveness in bringing out rancidity under anaerobic conditions. The results of the experiments are given in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Action of metals in presence and absence of oxygen on the development of rancidity in butterfat.

Expt. No.	Description.	Peroxide values after			
		15 days.	30 days.	45 days.	60 days.
1.	Control in air	0.1	1.3	2.4	3.0
2.	Copper oleate (5 p.p.m.) in presence of O ₂	1.50	5.6	14.4	30.0
3.	Copper oleate (5 p.p.m.) in absence of O ₂	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.25
4.	Cobalt oleate (5 p.p.m.) in presence of O ₂	2.5	7.2	22.9	36.2
5.	Cobalt oleate (5 p.p.m.) in absence of O ₂	—	—	0.0	0.15

From the results in Table IV it can be concluded that the harmful effect of the metals on fat is due to an acceleration of the normal process of oxidation; in absence of oxygen they are unable to produce this effect. A trace of an active metal added to the fat will reduce and may in some cases destroy the induction period of butterfat (Expt. 2, Table IV).

From the above results it appears that there exists no simple relation between the chemical properties of metals and their activities as accelerators of fat oxidation, but the generalisation of Mackey and Ingle seems to be useful as a rough guide. According to these authors, "in its oil soluble form a metal which exists in more than one state of oxidation acts as a drier or oxygen-carrier, provided that the salts of the lower oxides are more stable than the higher. The more oxides a metal can form, the greater is its catalytic power" (Mackey and Ingle, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1916, 35, 454).